

A Guideline for Video Compression for the Web in Earth Science

The **purpose** of this guideline is to describe essential encoding parameters used for web video encoding.

The **goal** of this document is to present the key considerations for each parameter in the context of creating web videos with a focus on the trade-off between quality and file size reduction.

The **scope** of this guideline applies to data hosts of scientific communities that want to provide the content of pristine source videos via smaller representations in the web.

Adhering to the guideline will **result** in data-optimized web videos, that offer a perfect balance between quality and file size.

Introduction

Encoding web videos is all about optimization.

To ensure a positive user experience even under poor network conditions, videos for web clients must be optimized for both file size and quality. Consequently, when encoding videos for the web, a trade-off must be found between reducing data and maintaining visual quality, while avoiding image artefacts. The objective is to identify which data from the original source video must be retained and which can be omitted without affecting the viewer's perception during playback and thus having an impact on the user experience.

Consequently, there are two aspects of significant importance in this trade-off process.

The first one is the video content itself and its impact on the temporal and spatial complexity. To achieve the same level of perceived video quality, videos with fast motion and small details, i.e., action movies, require higher data rates than videos with slow motion and large low-detail areas, i.e., cartoons.

The second one is the target playback device. A high-end television screen requires a completely different level of detail than a common monitor screen. For this reason, when encoding web videos, the encoding parameters should always be tailored to the content as well as the output device.

There are two common procedures to encode videos for the web.

The first one, video stream encoding, involves splitting the source video into multiple segments, while each segment is encoded within multiple representations with different bitrates, i.e., in different resolutions.

The second one does not split the source video, resulting in a contiguous file with a reduced bitrate. Consequently, the encoding process is less complex and requires fewer computing resources. Furthermore, if only one representation is encoded, it requires less storage space. However, it cannot adapt to changes in network bandwidth on client side, unlike the video stream approach.

This guideline focuses on web encoding of scientific videos for hosting on websites. Unlike entertainment films, scientific videos are usually not watched in one continuous piece. For instance, they capture the entire operation of a remote event, with several phases - i.e. camera start, travel to the research site, research activities at the site, return to the start - and can last several hours. As a result, not all parts of the video are equally significant. Moreover, the target audience for such publicly accessible research videos is typically a small community rather than the broader public. In order to maintain a good balance between views, playback time and data volume, this guideline describes the encoding of web videos via single web video preview files.

Encoding parameters for web videos

The choice of video encoding parameters has a direct impact on the quality of the encoded video and its file size. Consequently, it is crucial to select the appropriate parameters for effective web video encoding. This section presents the most essential web video encoding parameters, with the objective of encoding a single web video preview file from a pristine source file that can be used for playback on websites.

The proposed parameters are based on recordings made by researchers during ship expeditions, for instance, when utilizing underwater robots. Nevertheless, these parameters should be sufficiently robust for other natural sceneries. The web videos are created with the intention of playing them in web browsers on PCs, for instance, when working with media asset management systems or GIS-based map viewers.

The recommendations from this section are incorporated into a web video encoding command in the appendix, using the popular FFmpeg tool.

Parameter	Recommended	Not Recommended	Note
# Video			
Container	MP4, WebM		A widely used container for AVC is MP4, whereas WebM is the optimal choice for VP9.
Format / Codec	AVC (Advanced Video Codec, H.264), VP9		Trade-off between computational complexity, bit rate and browser compatibility. VP9 is more computational complex than H.264, but requires less bitrate with almost same browser compatibility. AV1 is very computationally intensive during encoding, but highly efficient. As browser support for AV1 increases, it may become more promising in the future.
Profile	Automatically set by encoder		It is recommended not to set a fixed profile. The encoder will automatically determine which profile is required based on the encoding settings. Using the parameters in this table will usually result in the High Profile.
Level	Automatically set by encoder		Based on the parameters in this table, it will result most often in High@L4.0.
Preset Option	Medium		Trade-off between encoding time and bit rate: Slower presets can reduce bits, however require more time.
GOP (=Group of Pictures)	Dynamic with maximum length of 2 seconds		Very high GOP lengths will result in slightly more efficient compression. However, video seeking gets more computational expensive due to the reduced amount of I-frames.
Bitrate Mode	CRF (Constant Rate Factor)		CRF: Encoding with constant quality. To avoid peak bit rates, capped CRF encoding can be used where a maximum bit rate and buffer size is specified.
CRF Value	25		For H.264, a CRF value of 0 results in technically lossless bitrate encoding. The default value is 23, while 51 produces the worst encoding quality.
Width	Based on height and aspect ratio		To prevent content warping, it is advisable to calculate the width automatically based on the height and aspect ratio. Additionally, it is best to avoid odd resolutions, such as 1921 pixels.

Height	Same as source, but limit to 1080	Height > 1080	To ensure smooth video playback under different network conditions, multiple web videos in various resolutions can be provided. However, if only one representation is used, it is recommended to limit the maximum height to 1080.
Aspect Ratio	Same as source		The website should be capable of integrating media with different aspect ratios into its layout, rather than forcing the media to adapt to the layout of a specific website. Therefore, there is no need to alter the video aspect ratio by adding black bars or warping the content.
Scan Type	Progressive (i.e., 1080p)	Interlaced (i.e., 1080i)	If deinterlacing is required, it is recommended to not increase the frame rate, i.e., one frame for each field. Instead, use a deinterlacing algorithm that keeps the frame rate to reduce the bit rate. Example: yadif=0 (output one frame for each frame) for 60i to 30p.
Frame rate / FPS	Same as source, but limit to 30 fps		Trade-off between data reduction and smoothness. For web videos, a maximum frame rate of 30 fps should be sufficient in most use cases.
Frame rate mode	Constant (CFR)		Variable Frame Rate (VFR) can introduce unpredictable variations in frame rate, potentially affecting the perceived smoothness and performance during playback.
Color space	YUV		This color space is ideal for reducing data through chroma subsampling.
Chroma subsampling	4:2:0		Due to humans' reduced ability to perceive color compared to luminance, the visual quality of the video is barely affected by chroma subsampling. However, it is possible to achieve a significant reduction in data.
Bit depth	8 bit		HDR (High Dynamic Range) allows a higher contrast ratio using more bits. However, for visualization on websites, playback with SDR (Standard Dynamic Range) should suffice.
# Audio			
Codec	AAC, Opus		Opus provides the same perceivable quality as AAC with fewer bits, hence it is more efficient. Currently, the support of Opus in MP4 is not flawless, thus it is recommended to use AAC for MP4 and Opus for WebM.
Channel Mixing	Stereo		Stereo sound should be sufficient to create an adequate immersive experience for most target users.
Bitrate	128 kbps (AAC), 96 kbps (Opus)		Opus provides the equivalent audio quality as AAC at a lower bitrate. In FFmpeg, the native AAC encoder requires a slightly higher bitrate, i.e., 160 kbps, than the libfdk_aac encoder for the same quality.
Sample Rate	Keep (max. 48 kHz)		Sampling rates above 48 kHz do not provide any additional perceivable information for human listeners.
# Metadata			
Moov Atom	Beginning of file		The Moov atom contains information about the structure of the video data. If it is at the beginning of the file, the player can start playback without loading the video completely. This is important for web videos.
Further metadata	Delete unnecessary data		Remove data that the user cannot see or that does not affect playback to avoid wasting bandwidth, such as subtitles, data and attachments.

Appendix:

FFmpeg command:

Command to encode videos for web browsers with FFmpeg 6.0 based on the recommendations given above. Replace <input> and <output> with the paths to the input file and the target output file.

```
ffmpeg -y
-stats -probesize 32M
-i <input>
-vf "[0:v] yadif=0 [deinterlaced];[deinterlaced] fps=fps=source_fps:start_time=0
[timeshifted];[timeshifted] scale=-2:ceil(ih*min(1,1080/ih)/2)*2 [video]"
-af "aresample=first_pts=0"
-vcodec libx264 -preset medium -crf 25 -pix_fmt yuv420p
-maxrate 5M -bufsize 12.5M
-force_key_frames "expr:gte(t,n_forced*2)" -fps_mode cfr -fpsmax 30
-acodec aac -channel_layout stereo -b:a 160k
-f mp4 -movflags +faststart -max_muxing_queue_size 1024 -timecode 0:00:00:00
-map -0:t? -sn -dn -map_metadata -1
<output>
```

References:

- Krämmer, C., Schoening, T., Schimpf, K. (2024). A Guideline for Image Compression in Earth Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11631187>
- Schoening, T., Durden, J.M., Faber, C. *et al.* Making marine image data FAIR. *Sci Data* **9**, 414 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01491-3>

Glossary:

- AVC / H.264:** Advanced Video Coding, also known as **H.264** - standard for video compression.
- CRF:** Constant Rate Factor – video encoding mode that adjusts the compression for each frame to receive a constant level of perceived quality for the entire video.
- FPS:** Frames Per Second – referring to the framerate, which is defined as the number of consecutive frames per second that should be played back from a video file.
- MP4:** Digital multimedia container format developed by MPEG and ISO.
- YUV:** Color space that considers the luminance and color perception of the human visual system. The human eye is more sensitive to brightness than to color, thus separating the luma component (**Y**) from the two chroma components, blue-difference (**U**) and red-difference (**V**), allows the chroma components to be reduced independently of the luminance.

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- Authors:** Christopher Krämmer, Timm Schoening
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- Abstract:** Due to the limited bandwidth available over networks, web video encoding aims to reduce the data rate while minimizing the impact on image quality. This guideline document describes essential encoding parameters for web video and how they affect data rate and video quality. Furthermore, it provides recommendations for natural footage, such as video recordings during marine expeditions.
- Note:** One-resolution web videos cannot provide all the advantages of video streams. However, they are significantly less complex in terms of computing power and storage requirements. Furthermore, developments in the field of video encoding are an ongoing process, resulting in continuous improvements in data efficiency. This is crucial for web videos, where the best possible video quality should be reproduced at the lowest possible bit rate. For this reason, the guideline should be seen as a snapshot within this ongoing process.
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Revisions:

Version	Date	Author	Comment
V1.0.0	2024/09	Christopher Krämmer	Initial draft of a public text version of this guideline. Compiled from discussions in the DataHub AG Videos/Images.